

Implementation of a Unit-Based Council

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Background

- The healthcare industry continues to face nursing shortages due to burnout and compassion fatigue
- The US average cost of turnover for one bedside registered nurse (RN) is \$40,038.
- Shared governance applied to healthcare has improved patient care and outcomes
- A unit-based council (UBC) is a form of a shared governance model that allows RNs to take ownership of their own practice
- A common theme in nursing resignations at an intensive care unit (ICU) department was the lack of professional development and growth

Problem Statement

There is no shared governance in an intensive care unit (ICU) department for nurses to address unit-specific problems while encouraging professional development and growth.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this QI project was to implement a shared-governance model known as a unit-based council and evaluate structural empowerment scores to encourage professional growth and development.

Methods

Staff RN in the critical care department was asked to participate in a fully anonymous survey titled “Conditions for Work Effectiveness (CWEQ I)” prior to the implementation of the UBC and after three months. The results of the survey were analyzed using a paired t-test.

Kanter’s Structural Empowerment Framework

Results

Two-Tailed Paired t-Test for the Difference Between December 2022 and February 2023

December 2022		February 2023		t	P	d
M	SD	M	SD			
2.55	0.74	3.11	0.64	-11.33	<.001	1.49

References

Results

- The sample size for pre- and post-implementation was 15 and 13 participants
- Structural empowerment scores increased in all topics after the initiation of UBC. The gross mean structural empowerment score increased from 2.55 to 3.11 from December 2022 to February 2023.

Discussion and limitations

Staff nurses were excited and responsive to have an opportunity to have input into how they provide care to their patients.

Several limitations were identified with this QI project:

- Short duration while UBC was effective
- Small sample size
- Continued nursing turnovers from various factors
- Multiple organizational changes occurring simultaneously

Recommendations

- Changing an organization / departments culture takes time
- Shared governance model is a partnership that requires both management and staff nurses to be successful
- A shared governance concept must be embodied into how the department operates and should start during the hiring process
- Other forms of shared governance staff nurses may participate in include hospital councils and themed councils
- Reassess at regular intervals to track structural empowerment scores